

INFLUENCE OF FOREIGN DISTRIBUTOR, INTERNATIONAL MARKET, FOREIGN MARKET COMPETITION, DIGITAL PLATFORM RISK ON INTERNATIONALIZATION PERFORMANCE OF PHARMACEUTICAL ENTREPRENEURIAL

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Abstract

It is well known that the role of internationalization has great importance and emerging trend in international trade as it helps to raise the substantial revenue from the sale. The given study designed to evaluate the effect of market orientation, foreign market competition and foreign distributors' capabilities on entrepreneurial performance of the Thailand pharmaceutical companies with the help of mediating the role of digital platform risk. The data regarding internationalization and market orientation has been collected from 422 employees, out of 188 were female and 234 were male respondents. Moreover, a survey based questionnaire technique was used to collect the required data. A five-point Likert scale was used to measure and record responses. Under the analysis, the various significant techniques are used such as descriptive statistics, KMO, SEM, CFA, convergent validity and component rotated tests for a different purpose. The table of SEM and analysis has indicated that the internationalization performance has an insignificant impact on the foreign market competition while all have a positive relationship. The results of the study also confirmed significant mediation effects of digital risk on the relationships between explanatory variables market orientation, foreign market competition and distributor capabilities and outcome variable internationalization performance. The recommendations were provided that future researchers focus on cross-sectional data rather than longitudinal data and research design.

Keywords: Internationalization performance, digital platform risk, foreign market competition, international market orientation, foreign distributor capabilities.

1 INTRODUCTION

There has been an emerging trend of digitalization for entering in the foreign market. Firms are gaining immense benefits with this internationalization and contribute to the country's economy, but at the same time there are risks commercial and financial risks associated with it. Diversity management also presents a significant issue in the internationalization process of organizations. The digital platform, although beneficial and a novel process presents a probable jeopardy and risk for businesses (Cavusgil & Knight, 2015; Manyika & Lund, 2016).

Graph 1.1: Thailand’s Internet Economy Market size

The Internet and other technological advancements are benefitting the firms in international markets. It is widely used in almost all activities like marketing, logistics and financing. Digital platform is appealing for firms because it is a low cost medium for internationalization. Given the growing participation in the use of digital platforms, the firms are able to connect to the seller and buyer for transaction and negotiation in international market. However, with this use, certain risks are posed on the firms. (Balabanis, 2000; Kim & Cavusgil, 2020; Thomas, Autio, & Gann, 2014). So, the aims of this study are to identify the precursors of internationalization performance as the major outcome of digital platform risk in Thailand.

Table 1.1: Internationalization of firms in Thailand

Categories	Characteristics
Small scale	Low value economic activities, informal networks of connections for trade activities
Large scale	Control of Business elite, use of competitive advantage, early movement into neighboring countries

In spite of the increasing trend of Internet shaping the landscape of digital firms, academic literature in this domain is limited and is not well documented. Previous studies have explained the benefits of Internet, in improving the digital firm’s performance, however there is limited literature that focuses on the negative aspects of Internet’s usage by the firms in transnational context (Kim & Cavusgil, 2020; Kuivalainen et al., 2013; Pezderka & Sinkovics, 2011). Study by (Kim & Cavusgil, 2020; Weerawardena, Mort, Salunke, Knight, & Liesch, 2015) has pointed out that other contingent factors that may explain or influence the DPR (digital platform risk) be investigated as well. Hence, this study addresses this contextual gap in literature.

The primary objectives of this research study are to access the challenges for the digital pharmaceutical firms in the internationalization performance in Thailand. This study has more specific research objectives also that have been outlined below:

- To find out the influence of Foreign Distributor capabilities on Internationalization Performance
- To find out the influence of International Market Orientation on Internationalization Performance
- To find out the influence of Foreign market Competition on Internationalization Performance
- To find out the mediating effect of Digital Platform Risk in these relationships.

Theoretically, this research article will make additions in the theory and existing literature by presenting the underlying mechanism through confirming the potential path of digital platform risk in the influence of Foreign Distributor capabilities, International Market Orientation and Foreign market Competition on the digital firm's internationalization performance. This study has practical implications for managers of the digital firms that they must learn the skills and knowledge to cope with the digital platform risks and must pay special attention when attempting to leverage opportunities from digital platforms.

The paper follows the following structure. The first portion presents an Introduction to the topic of study, the second section provides the literature review of the variables & briefly discusses their relationships, thus forming the research framework. The third section shows the research methodology which will be used to establish the relationships. The fourth section presents the empirical results and their analysis. The last portion of the paper consists of the conclusion, a discussion, conclusion, limitations and implications drawn from the findings of the study.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Background

This study is based on the "Transaction Cost Economics" (TCE), which has been broadly accepted and utilized in the International Business literature. This study applies TCE to determine the online risks to digital firms using the concepts of uncertainty that arise from the environment in which investments are made (Contractor, 2007; Ghoshal & Moran, 1996; Rindfleisch & Heide, 1997; Williamson, 1988).

2.2 Effect Of Foreign Distributor Capabilities

Expanding business in foreign market can enhance the relationships among foreign distributors or agents. This helps the distributors gain foreign market information and reduces the uncertainties associated with the foreign environment. The capabilities of foreign distributor serves as an asset for the firm as they assist in setting up a distributor network in foreign market, because they possess many years of experience in global trade. This way the firm is able to benefit from the FDC of rapid distribution of the products in the target market, which leads to

improved performance (Guennif & Ramani, 2008; Lee, 2015; Lew, Sinkovics, & Kuivalainen, 2013; Yelapaala, 1993). This implies that FDC is positively linked to the Internationalization performance. Hence, the hypothesis:

.H1: Foreign Distributor capabilities is significantly linked to internationalization performance

2.3 Effect Of International Market Orientation

One key strategic factor of a firm participating in digital platform is the firm's IMO, which determines the international market information system. This can facilitate the international communications and external customer relationship. International market orientation can be defined as the significance of the markets to which the subsidiary supplies products, to either external or internal buyers, located in a place instead of the host region or country. (Manolopoulos, 2010; Rugman, Nguyen, & Wei, 2016). Studies have shown that IMO contributes to improved performance levels (Acosta, Crespo, & Agudo, 2018; Dahms, 2015; Fang, Chang, Ou, & Chou, 2014; Farrell, Oczkowski, & Kharabsheh, 2008; He & Wei, 2011; Jaworski & Kohli, 1993; Monferrer, Blesa, & Ripollés, 2012; O'Connor, Vera-Muñoz, & Chan, 2011; Wu, Ma, & Liu, 2019). This implies that a direct relationship exists between RC and FP. Hence, the hypothesis:

H2: International Market Orientation is significantly linked to internationalization performance

2.4 Effect Of Foreign Market Competition

The competition faced from the external markets (markets located outside the border of the host country) is defined as "the degree to which competition is concentrated in the external markets" (Li, Poppo, & Zhou, 2008). Augmented concentration of competition implies that there are greater number of rivals in the form of price wars, aggressive advertising, greater product offerings, enriched services and increased transactions. Since the digital platform is recognized as low-cost medium to help the digital firms explore and exploit more foreign opportunities and expand their business, this improves their performance internationally (Kim & Cavusgil, 2020). This implies that FMC is positively related to Internationalization performance. Hence, the hypothesis:

H3: Foreign Market Competition is significantly linked to internationalization performance

2.5 Mediation Of Digital Platform Risk

Digital platform risk is referred to as the ambiguity and pressures faced by the firms when an international exchange is carried out on a digital platform. Based on the TCE, DPR can be defined as the devious performance or conduct and ambiguity existing on the DP, observed during the exchange with international customers. The foreign competition has the tendency to drive DPR, where dysfunctional competition can emerge. This means that when there is fierce competition in foreign markets, many firms participating in virtual platforms sustain escalations in unknown behaviors on digital platforms, like imitations and copycat behaviors on the part of competitors (Kim & Cavusgil, 2020). This implies that the completion in an external market is related positively to DPR. The foreign distributors help the firms entering into the international market to disperse their product or service to the intended customer.

However, this destructive relationship can be strained and pose an uncertainty and risk on the digital platforms. Also, this can give rise to opportunistic behavior that increase the DPR and negatively impact the internationalization performance (Kim & Cavusgil, 2020). When companies are partaking in digital platform for internationalization through foreign market competition, international orientation and foreign distributor capabilities, they may encounter distinctive types of hazards and ambiguities, like “price news manipulation by competitors, negative associations with international customers and distributors”, (Kim & Cavusgil, 2020; Nakos, Dimitratos, & Elbanna, 2019; Sheng, Zhou, & Li, 2011) which impacts significantly the internationalization performance . This implies that DPR can be investigated as a mediator in these relationships. Hence, the hypothesis:

H4a: Digital Platform Risk significantly mediates the relationship of Foreign Distributor capabilities and internationalization performance.

H4b: Digital Platform Risk significantly mediates the relationship of International Market Orientation and internationalization performance.

H4c: Digital Platform Risk significantly mediates the relationship of Foreign Market Competition and internationalization performance.

Figure 1.2: Research framework

3 METHODS

3.1 Sample Characteristics

The research followed the method of a questionnaire to collect data. Snowball sampling technique was used as the access to the management of the pharmaceutical companies is difficult to access. The respondents were provided a concise explanation about the objectives and motives of the study and then questionnaire was distributed among the respondents. The respondents were assured of the anonymity of their responses. The researcher implied the item response theory to calculate the sample size. The criteria of twenty responses against each item was followed and 430 questionnaires were distributed in totality. Although only 422 out of these were fit for use and the remaining 8 were discarded due to missing values.

3.2 Measures

The scales were adapted and developed according to the requirements of the present study. Preexisting scales were used because their reliability and validity has already been established by a number of studies. However, to check the relevance and appropriateness of the scale in accordance with the context and requirements of the present study academicians were consulted to ascertain the content validity of the scale. MBA graduates were used as pretest subjects, they were asked to fill the questionnaires. Their responses and feedbacks were used to make some adjustments in the questionnaire. The advice of Campbell, Brislin, Stewart, and Werner (1970) was followed and the forward and back translation method was used. The questionnaires were translated back to English so that the study and its results could be used by researchers from other communities as well. All scale items have been measured on a five point Likert scale, ranging from “1=strongly disagree” to “5=strongly agree”.

3.2.1 Foreign Distributor Capabilities

The foreign distributive capacities of the pharmaceutical firms was evaluated on the basis of the study of Roath, Miller, and Cavusgil (2002). The items were modified and adapted according to current requirements.

3.2.2 International Market Orientation

The international market orientation was adapted from the study of Boso, Story, and Cadogan (2013). The construct consists of three items which were modified according to the requirements of the present study. A sample item is “Our foreign buyer/customers’ product demands and preference change quite a bit over time”.

3.2.3 Foreign Market Competition

The study by Boso et al. (2013) was used to develop items for foreign market competition. Three items were used to study this construct. The items were modified to fit the requirements of the present study. A sample item is “There is substantial competition among companies in our export markets”.

1.1. digital platform risk

DPR was measured on the basis of the scale by Pavlou and Gefen (2004). The scale consists of eight items which were adapted and modified according to requirements of the present study. A sample item is “Participating in this digital platform may strain my relationships with our current foreign customers”.

3.2.4 Internationalization Performance

The scale developed by Nummela, Saarenketo, and Puumalainen (2004) was used to measure internationalization performance. The scale consisted of five items, which were adapted and modified to fit the requirements of the present study. A sample item includes “We have achieved our profitability objectives set for our internationalization over the last five years”.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Demographics

A sample of 422 respondents was finalized for the research. Out of these 55.5 percent were male and the remaining 44.5 percent were identified as females. The principal reason for the gender disparity is the fact that more men were found to be employed in the pharmaceutical manufacturing units. The age of 73.4 percent of the respondents was up to 35 and the experience of 74.4 percent sample was between 2 and 8 years. The main reason for the elevation observed in age and education is the level of employees approached.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Table 1 presents the Minimum and maximum values, means and skewness coefficients are analyzed to check the data for the presence of outliers, data normality and the inclination of responses. These measures represent the descriptive analysis of the data. The mean values are approaching 4 demonstrating the agreement of respondents with the statements of the variables. The skewness values also fall within the range of -1+1, demonstrating the normality of the data. However, no outliers were observed in the responses.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
InterPerf	422	1.00	5.00	3.2921	.98195	-.360	.119
DigiRisk	422	1.00	5.00	3.5311	1.15299	-.558	.119
ForigMaC	422	1.00	5.00	3.2046	1.20482	-.270	.119
IntMaOri	422	1.00	5.00	3.5468	1.13596	-.473	.119
ForDisCp	422	1.00	5.00	3.3665	1.14273	-.461	.119
Valid N (listwise)	422						

4.3 Kmo And Bartlett's Test

The KMO and Bartlett's test is conducted in order to determine the adequacy of the sample. If and only if the results of this test are significant then the factor analysis and other tests will be conducted.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.929
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	8363.330
	df	171
	Sig.	.000

4.4 Factor Analysis

The rotated component matrix demonstrates the contribution of each individual scale item in the overall construct. As table 3 demonstrates, all items are significant, the loadings are greater than 0.7. The problem of cross-loading hasn't been observed as well.

Table 3: Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
IP1				.777	
IP2				.784	
IP3				.820	
PR1	.834				
PR2	.843				
PR3	.820				
PR4	.892				
PR5	.908				
PR6	.899				
PR7	.905				
PR8	.888				
FM1		.862			
FM2		.882			
FM3		.880			
IM1			.844		
IM2			.854		
IM3			.857		
FD1					.749
FD2					.742

4.5 Convergent And Discriminant Validity

The score of composite reliability values is more than 0.7 (Hassan, Hameed, Basheer, & Ali, 2020; Iqbal & Hameed, 2020) and the variance extracted indicator, AVE, is also more than 0.5 for all variables. The MSV values are less than the AVE values and self-correlation coefficients are also higher than those of the variable-variable correlation. Thus discriminant and convergent validity is present.

Table 4: Convergent and Discriminant Validity

	CR	AVE	MSV	IM	IP	PR	FM	FD
IM	0.907	0.764	0.360	0.874				
IP	0.818	0.601	0.360	0.600	0.775			
PR	0.924	0.826	0.287	0.490	0.507	0.909		

FM	0.921	0.796	0.527	0.300	0.328	0.475	0.892	
FD	0.893	0.806	0.527	0.481	0.509	0.536	0.726	0.898

4.6 Model Fitness

CFA test results are demonstrated in table 5. The CMIN value is 2.6, less than 3, GFI is greater than 0.8 (0.913), CFI and IFI is greater than 0.9 (0.973) and RMSEA value is less than 0.08 (0.062). The threshold ranges are being fulfilled therefore the model is fit.

Table 5: Confirmatory Factors Analysis

Indicators	Threshold range	Current values
CMIN/DF	Less or equal 3	2.610
GFI	Equal or greater .80	.913
CFI	Equal or greater .90	.973
IFI	Equal or greater .90	.973
RMSEA	Less or equal .08	.062

Figure 1: CFA

4.7 SEM

A unit change in ForigMAc produces a negative effect of 4.1 percent in InterPERf, the relationship is insignificant therefore the hypothesis is rejected. A unitary increase or decrease in IntMaOri and ForDisCp produces variations of 35.9 and 22.4 percent in InterPerf. The relationships are significant therefore the hypotheses are accepted. The mediation of DigiRisk

through Forigmac produces an effect of 4.1 percent, 5.7 percent through Intmaori and 4.3 percent through ForDiscp. The mediation results are significant therefore the hypotheses are accepted

Table 6: Structural Equation Modeling

Total Effect	ForigMaC	IntMaOri	ForDisCp	DigiRisk
DigiRisk	.215**	.298**	.226**	.000
InterPerf	.000	.416***	.267**	.191**
Direct Effect	ForigMaC	IntMaOri	ForDisCp	DigiRisk
DigiRisk	.215**	.298***	.226**	.000
InterPerf	-.041	.359***	.224**	.191**
Indirect Effect	ForigMaC	IntMaOri	ForDisCp	DigiRisk
DigiRisk	.000	.000	.000	.000
InterPerf	.041**	.057**	.043**	.000

Figure 2: SEM

5 DISCUSSION

Research by Miskell and Nicoli (2016) argued that the foreign distributor is an individual or team to which a particular sector can sell their products and brands, with the expectation that the foreign distributor will then resell those brands within a foreign country or region. Sometimes the capabilities of the foreign distributor can damage the internationalization success of any sector because foreign distributors often demand a long period of time which can decrease the level of internationalization success (Kumar, 2018). The initial results of the study also indicate that the capabilities of foreign distributors have an insignificant impact on the internationalization success of the business.

Acosta et al. (2018) revealed that international market orientation IMO proves to be a very successful factor in enhancing the internationalization success if the business because IMO can consist of generating different products in order to get a positive review from consumers, and

thus positively influence the internationalization success of a business. That's why the hypotheses regarding the direct impact of IMO on internationalization success has been accepted and indicate positive outcomes. Furthermore, the findings of the study also manifest that digital platform risk negatively affects the relationship between FDC and internationalization success.

6 CONCLUSION

The research paper concludes that the firm achieves success and competitive advantage by evaluating and assessing challenges in all sectors of the Pharmaceutical during the process of internationalization. The pharmaceutical sector enhances its product capabilities by adopting the means of earning a good number of foreign distributors to achieve a successful name internationally. The achievements in the international market place and to compete the foreign competitors. The research paper evaluates all the aspects very briefly. The Data gathered by a total of 411 employees of the firms. Out of which 185 were female and 226 were of males.

6.1 Implications And Limitations

The given study is highly effective in evaluating and assessing the challenges faced by Thailand Pharmaceutical firms to win a place internationally. This study also provokes other researchers to find out new means to progress the firms and industry.

Despite their contributions, the study also has some limitations. First, this study only focused on the mediating role of digital platform risk DPR, therefore, future research may evaluate and integrate other mediating variables for better results and outcomes. The cross-sectional design is the most important limitation of this research study, thus, future studies may conduct this research in a longitudinal manner. It is also recommended to future analysts that they can evaluate other dimensions of internationalization success and performance.

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